

Historical perspectives and emerging trends in fentanyl use: Part 1 – Pharmacological profile

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Abstract

Fentanyl, a potent synthetic opioid, is widely used for severe pain management and anesthesia but poses significant risks due to its extreme potency and addictive potential. It acts primarily on μ -opioid receptors, with additional effects on κ - and δ -receptors, producing analgesia and adverse effects, such as respiratory depression, mediated via G-protein and β -arrestin signaling pathways. Fentanyl's pharmacokinetics include rapid onset and a short duration, with extensive liver metabolism via CYP3A4 enzymes. Its high lipophilicity allows it to cross the blood-brain barrier quickly, contributing to its rapid central nervous system effects and associated risk of respiratory depression. Despite its therapeutic value, fentanyl's potential to induce tolerance and dependence, coupled with escalating illicit use, underscores the need for enhanced prevention strategies, improved overdose management, and stricter regulatory measures to balance therapeutic utility with abuse prevention.

Keywords

fentanyl, opioids, G-protein, β -arrestin

Introduction

For millennia, *Papaver somniferum* L. (Papaveraceae), commonly known as the opium poppy, has been cultivated for its analgesic and medicinal properties. Opium, a latex extracted from the seed capsules of this plant, contains the natural alkaloids morphine and codeine, which are classified as opiates (Suzuki and El-Haddad 2016). The term 'opioid' was later introduced to encompass not only these opiates but also endogenous opioid peptides (such as enkephalins, endorphins, and dynorphins) and subsequently developed semi-synthetic and synthetic compounds (Dolinak 2017; Jutkiewicz and Traynor 2023;

World Health Organization 2023). Opioid medications are often referred to as narcotic analgesics or simply narcotics, a term derived from the Greek "narkōtikos", meaning 'numbing' or 'stupor', referring to their sedative properties and ability to induce sleep in response to pain (Jutkiewicz and Traynor 2023; World Health Organization 2023).

The opioid portfolio has expanded to include various synthetic molecules developed as more potent analgesics with improved safety profiles compared to natural opiates. A prominent example is fentanyl, a 4-anilidopiperidine derivative and the most widely used synthetic opioid for managing severe pain and surgical anesthesia (Fig. 1) (Stanley 2014; Han et al. 2019; Kelly et al. 2023).

Figure 1. Chemical structure of fentanyl.

Despite over half a century of medical use, fentanyl's pharmacological profile continues to stimulate research interest. A key motivation for elucidating its pharmacokinetics and intricate mechanism of action was the reduced efficacy of naloxone in acute fentanyl intoxication compared to older opioids (Moss and Carlo 2019). Recent findings on the intracellular signaling pathways—both G-protein- and β -arrestin-mediated—activated by opioid receptor stimulation have yielded novel insights, enhancing the understanding of opioid safety profiles and guiding the development of new, safer generations of opioid therapeutics (de Waal PW et al. 2020). Additionally, the complex and specific indications for this opioid analgesic have led to numerous innovations in its delivery systems (Schug and Ting 2017).

A comprehensive understanding of fentanyl's pharmacokinetics, mechanism of action, dosing, and formulations has laid the groundwork for its safe clinical use. In the context of the global opioid epidemic, knowledge of fentanyl's pharmaceutical properties supports improved regulation and abuse prevention. These insights can guide the development of safer formulations and more effective strategies to control its distribution and misuse. Thus, the present review aims to inform healthcare professionals and public health workers about the latest pharmaceutical aspects of fentanyl, thereby supporting efforts to address the so-called “opioid crisis”—the significant increase in opioid overuse, misuse, and fatal overdoses, primarily in the United States (US), encompassing both prescription and illicit opioids (Vadivelu et al. 2018).

Methods

For the purpose of this review, data were collected and analyzed from leading scientific databases, including PubMed, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and ResearchGate, providing current and peer-reviewed publications on the pharmacological characteristics of fentanyl. It includes documents published between the years 1980 and 2025. The research employed the following keywords and their combinations: fentanyl, fentanyl toxicity, fentanyl-related overdose, fentanyl analogues, illicit fentanyl, synthetic opioids, opioid epidemic, opioid crisis, and opioid overdose prevention. Additionally, official data from recognized authoritative and regulatory sources, such as the World Health Organization, European Commission, European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction, European Union Drugs Agency, and Bulgarian drug agency, were utilized. The data from these sources were

gathered to provide a comprehensive overview of the current pharmacological knowledge on the opioid of interest.

Results and discussion

Development of fentanyl: Evolution and innovation in drug delivery

In the 1960s, a research team led by Belgian pharmacologist Paul Janssen aimed to overcome the limitations of available opioids, such as morphine and meperidine. These opioids were considered weak and slow-acting due to their limited penetration of the central nervous system (CNS). In 1960, the team developed fentanyl, a more lipophilic and potent compound that readily crosses the blood-brain barrier (BBB) and has a significantly higher therapeutic index (277 vs. 4.7 and 71 for meperidine and morphine, respectively) (Poklis 1995; Stanley 2014).

In the early 1960s, fentanyl was successfully introduced into European clinical practice. Its intravenous pharmaceutical formulations were introduced in combination with a number of sedatives, hypnotics, and anesthetics to achieve general anesthesia (Suzuki and El-Haddad 2016). A particularly popular combination is that of fentanyl and droperidol, known as neuroleptanalgesia (or neuroleptanesthesia when nitrous oxide is co-administered)—an approach that is still utilized in some countries in Eastern Europe and South America (Stanley 2014).

Initially, the approval of fentanyl in the US faced resistance due to its high potency, risk of life-threatening rigidity, and potential for abuse. As a compromise, in 1968, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved fentanyl only in combination with droperidol in a 1:50 ratio (Innovar in the US or Thalamonal in other countries). Fentanyl became available as a standalone injectable solution (Sublimaze[®]) four years later. Over the following decades, neuroleptanalgesia and neuroleptanesthesia lost popularity in Europe and the US due to the lack of standardized techniques and the associated health risks (Stanley 2014).

By the late 1970s and early 1980s, fentanyl's use in cardiac and vascular surgery led to a tenfold increase in its US sales. High-dose applications during cardiac procedures further contributed to its growing popularity. Simultaneously, the expiration of its patent protection, coupled with its cost-effective production, facilitated its widespread adoption (Stanley 2014). The global increase in fentanyl use during the 1980s spurred the development of new fentanyl analogs, such as sufentanil, alfentanil, and remifentanil, which were approved for intravenous anesthesia. Carfentanil, approximately 10,000 times more potent than morphine, was developed for veterinary use, specifically to immobilize large wild animals (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime 2017; Jutkiewicz and Traynor 2023). While some of these analogs offer superior pharmacokinetic profiles, fentanyl remains effective and extensively studied. As a result, most research into new drug delivery methods for fentanyl-based compounds has focused on it.

In the 1980s, the first transdermal fentanyl patch (Duragesic[®]) was developed for chronic pain management, providing stable plasma concentrations for 2 to 3 days. This success led to the development of additional equivalents by generic manufacturers. Subsequently, oral transmucosal fentanyl citrate (OTFC) products, such as Oralet[®] (1993) and Actiq[®] (1998), were introduced to provide preoperative sedation, analgesia, and anxiolysis, as well as to treat breakthrough pain (BTP) in opioid-tolerant patients (Stanley 2014). The success of these products led to further exploration of faster-onset delivery systems, culminating in the approval of the oral transmucosal buccal tablet Fentora in 2006, which achieved higher plasma levels of the active ingredient in a shorter time. Additional formulations, including sublingual tablets, buccal dissolvable films, and nasal and sublingual sprays, have since been developed to provide rapid-onset analgesia. As a result, the pharmaceutical products containing fentanyl are categorized into two main groups (Kuczyńska et al. 2018; Jutkiewicz and Traynor 2023):

Rapid-onset opioids (ROOs)

This group includes injectable forms, oral transmucosal lozenges, buccal tablets, sublingual tablets, and intranasal sprays. These formulations are designed to provide rapid analgesic effects, suitable for acute pain management.

Fentanyl transdermal patches (FTP)

These are used for long-term analgesia in the treatment of persistent chronic pain. Currently, two types of transdermal delivery systems are employed. The first is a reservoir-based system, in which the medication is contained within a reservoir placed between two membranes. The second is a matrix patch, where fentanyl is suspended in a gel matrix within the silicone adhesive layer, which makes it more difficult to isolate for the purpose of misuse.

Current understanding of fentanyl's pharmacological profile

Pharmacodynamics

Fentanyl is a potent and selective μ -opioid receptor agonist that acts on various regions of the brain and spinal cord (European Commission 2011). Additionally, the drug exhibits notable affinity for κ - and δ -opioid receptors ($\mu \gg \kappa > \delta$), contributing to its broader range of biological effects (Table 1) (Kuczyńska et al. 2018; Torralva et al. 2020; Patocka et al. 2024).

Depending on the route of administration, fentanyl is approximately 50–100 times more potent than morphine and 30–50 times more potent than heroin (Poklis 1995). Unfortunately, this characteristic also makes fentanyl attractive for illicit trafficking, as smaller quantities of the pure substance can be more easily concealed and distributed, significantly reducing legal risks and smuggling costs (United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime 2023).

The main targets for the pharmacological action of fentanyl—opioid receptors—belong to the superfamily of G-protein-coupled receptors. These receptors are membrane-bound proteins characterized by seven transmembrane helices with intracellular and extracellular loops. They are widely distributed in both the peripheral and CNS and can be located pre- or postsynaptically (Jutkiewicz and Traynor 2023). Their activation elicits a variety of effects that depend on the type and location of the receptor. Specifically, the biological effects of the μ -opioid agonist fentanyl result from its interaction with inhibitory $G_{i/o}$ -proteins (Pathan and Williams 2012; Borsodi 2023; Jutkiewicz and Traynor 2023; Dhaliwal and Gupta 2024). This signaling pathway is mediated by the heterotrimer $G\alpha\beta\gamma$ (with the $G\alpha$ subunit bound to guanosine diphosphate, GDP). The activation of the receptor induces a conformational change that facilitates the conversion of GDP to guanosine triphosphate (GTP). As a result, $G\alpha\beta\gamma$ dissociates into the GTP-bound $G\alpha$ subunit and the heterodimer $G\beta\gamma$. Subsequently, $G\alpha$ inhibits adenylate cyclase, leading to decreased production of cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP), which affects membrane repolarization. $G\beta\gamma$ inhibits voltage-gated Ca^{2+} channels, resulting in reduced neurotransmitter release, and activates K^+ channels, causing neuronal hyperpolarization and decreased neurotransmitter release. Thus, G-proteins are directly involved in the analgesic effects of μ -agonists (Pathan and Williams 2012). Opioids may also stimulate the formation of cAMP, phosphoinositide hydrolysis, and an increase in intracellular Ca^{2+} by mobilizing from intracellular stores and stimulating influx. At the cellular level, these changes may underlie the opioid-induced stimulation of neuronal activity (Smart and Lambert 1996).

Long-term pharmacological studies have shown that μ -receptors also participate in G-protein-independent signaling through so-called β -arrestin complexes (Manglik 2016; Schmid 2017). Although both β -arrestin and G-protein signaling pathways are initiated by the same receptor, they can trigger distinct intracellular signaling cascades (Fig. 2). A key aspect of the β -arrestin signaling pathway is the receptor kinase-catalyzed phosphorylation of serine and threonine residues located at the C-terminus or

Table 1. Biological effects modulated by opioid receptors.

Receptors	Effects of agonism
μ_1, μ_2 u μ_3	The μ_1 receptor is responsible for the onset of analgesia and dependence; The μ_2 receptor plays a role in euphoria, respiratory depression, miosis, reduced gastrointestinal motility, and dependence; The μ_3 receptor is associated with vasodilation.
δ_1 u δ_2	They are associated with spinal and supraspinal analgesia, as well as reduced gastric motility.
κ_1, κ_2 u κ_3	They play a role in the expression of analgesia, diuresis, and dysphoria.

Figure 2. The G-protein and β -arrestin signaling pathways of μ -opioid receptors.

intracellular loops of the opioid receptor. This leads to the recruitment of β -arrestins, which promote receptor internalization and desensitization, potentially resulting in the manifestation of various adverse effects associated with opioids (Comer and Cahill 2019). This hypothesis is supported by studies in β -arrestin knockout mice, which exhibit prolonged opioid-induced analgesia, increased resistance to respiratory depression, constipation, dependence, and tolerance (Bohn et al. 1999, 2000, 2002; Raehal et al. 2005; Raehal and Bohn 2011; Bateman and Levitt 2021).

The presented data suggest that assessing the propensity to activate G-protein and/or β -arrestin signaling pathways could aid the development of safer opioid analgesics (de Waal 2020; Patocka et al. 2024). Recent drug design strategies, in particular, focus on differentiating between dual-function agonists and biased agonists. Dual-function agonists act on the μ -opioid receptor and concurrently target non-opioid receptors to provide therapeutic effects with fewer adverse effects than traditional opioids. Biased agonists, however, bind to the μ -opioid receptor but preferentially activate specific signaling pathways (Schmid et al. 2017; Jutkiewicz and Traynor 2023; Patocka et al. 2024). For instance, fentanyl acts as a β -arrestin-biased ligand, which likely contributes to its elevated risk of severe respiratory depression and mortality (Raehal and Bohn 2011; Comer and Cahill 2019; Patocka 2024). Conversely, the design of novel opioid receptor agonists biased toward G-protein-mediated signaling, such as Oliceridine, may improve the therapeutic index while minimizing side effects (Baumann et al. 2018).

Recent studies have increasingly focused on the interactions of fentanyl with non-opioid receptors, particularly in relation to severe adverse effects such as muscle rigidity, cardiovascular dysfunction, and laryngospasm, which are thought to be α -adrenergically mediated (Haxhiu et

al. 2003; Ge et al. 2015). Fentanyl inhibits the intracellular reuptake of norepinephrine while selectively blocking specific α 1-adrenergic receptor subtypes, concentrating noradrenergic activity on α 1D receptors and leading to coronary vasoconstriction and impaired cardiovascular function (Torralva et al. 2020). Additionally, fentanyl weakly blocks dopamine receptors, particularly D1 and D4 subtypes. As noted by Torralva et al. (2020), blockade of D1 receptors may exacerbate μ -mediated respiratory depression, potentially requiring higher doses of naloxone for opioid overdose reversal (Torralva et al. 2020). Another key dopaminergic mechanism involves fentanyl's binding to μ -opioid receptors on GABA-releasing neurons in the mesolimbic system, inhibiting GABA release, which typically moderates dopamine release. This disinhibition increases dopamine levels, contributing to profound euphoria and reinforcing fentanyl's high potential for addiction and abuse (Comer and Cahill 2019; Karunarathna 2024; Yarotsky et al. 2024).

Pharmacokinetics

Fentanyl is highly lipophilic compared to other opioid agonists. Due to its low molecular weight, it rapidly diffuses across biological membranes, including the BBB. This characteristic accounts for the relatively rapid onset of both analgesia and potentially fatal respiratory depression, which can persist for an extended duration (US Pharmacopeia 2024). The analgesic effect occurs within 1–2 minutes following intravenous (*i.v.*) administration, within 5–10 minutes after sublingual or intranasal spray use or intramuscular injection, and within 10–15 minutes following buccal transmucosal application. In contrast, following the application of a transdermal fentanyl patch, peak or plateau effects are observed after 8–16 hours

(Stanley 2014; Armenian et al. 2018; Patocka et al. 2024; US Pharmacopeia 2024). The transdermal route of administration begins with absorption through the skin, followed by passage into the cutaneous microcirculation, and ultimately entry into the systemic circulation. Absorption continues gradually for approximately 12 hours after the patch is removed, as the drug forms a depot on the skin (2–3% of the drug may remain on the skin up to 48 hours post-application) (Oliveira et al. 2012).

Fentanyl pharmacokinetics are best described by a three-compartment model. Upon entry into the systemic circulation, it rapidly distributes from the plasma to highly vascularized tissues, followed by redistribution to muscle and adipose compartments and eventual release back into the plasma. Consequently, fentanyl has an elimination half-life of approximately 3–8 hours (McClain and Hug 1980; Bulgarian drug agency 2022). Reflecting its high affinity, its tissue concentrations exceed those in plasma. It turns out that the plasma concentrations rather parallel those in the highly perfused areas (Hug and Murphy 1981). Fentanyl exhibits a volume of distribution of approximately 4 L/kg, with over 80% bound to plasma proteins—primarily albumin and, to a lesser extent, α_1 -acid glycoprotein (DrugBank 2024).

Fentanyl has a relatively short duration of action that is attributed to the activity of efflux P-glycoproteins in the BBB (Ziesenitz and van den Anker 2013). Its redistribution from the brain to peripheral tissues, along with its biotransformation, also terminates the central effects. Additionally, muscular distribution contributes to skeletal rigidity, including that of the chest wall (the ‘wooden chest syndrome’). Additionally, distribution in peripheral tissues can lead to drug accumulation in individuals using it systemically, potentially resulting in delayed clearance and a secondary plasma concentration peak (Kelly et al. 2023). The last effect is clinically significant, as it is possible for it to be accompanied by a recurrence of respiratory distress severe enough to necessitate the use of an antidote (Bird et al. 2023).

Fentanyl is primarily metabolized in the liver, predominantly by the cytochrome P450 enzymes CYP3A4, with minor contributions from CYP3A5 and CYP3A7 (Lötsch et al. 2013). It undergoes extensive first-pass clearance in the intestinal wall and liver, primarily through N-dealkylation of the piperidine ring to norfentanyl, accounting for over 99% of its metabolism in humans. Additional metabolic pathways include amide hydrolysis to despropionylfentanyl and alkyl hydroxylation to hydroxylfentanyl, with the latter further N-dealkylated to hydroxynorfentanyl. This presystemic elimination reduces fentanyl’s oral bioavailability to approximately 32%. Following intravenous administration, about 75% of the dose is excreted in urine, primarily as metabolites, with less than 10% as unchanged drug, while around 9% appears in feces as metabolites (Armenian 2018; DrugBank 2024; Patocka 2024). Metabolism occurs rapidly, with metabolites detectable in plasma within 90 seconds of intravenous administration. After 72 hours, most of the parent compound has been metabolized (McClain and Hug 1980). Concurrent use of fentanyl with CYP3A4 inhibitors, including certain

protease inhibitors, ketoconazole, fluconazole, diltiazem, erythromycin, and verapamil, may significantly increase plasma fentanyl concentrations, posing a risk of fatal respiratory depression. Consequently, patients on such drug combinations should be closely monitored for opioid overdose symptoms (Stanley 2014). Fentanyl itself may also inhibit enzyme activity, reducing the clearance of sedative drugs such as midazolam (Comer and Cahill 2019).

The influence of severe pain syndrome in patients who have not been treated with opioids may occur at low plasma concentrations ranging from 0.2 to 1.2 ng/mL. Conversely, individuals with opioid tolerance require higher concentrations, which can vary significantly on an interindividual basis (Stanley 2014). The recommended serum concentration for effective analgesia is up to 2 ng/mL, beyond which the risk of adverse drug reactions increases substantially (Lötsch et al. 2013). Reported EC_{50} values for respiratory depression, reduction in ventilation volume, and maximal EEG slowing with fentanyl are 3.5 ± 1.4 ng/mL, 6.1 ± 1.4 ng/mL, and 6.9 ± 1.5 ng/mL, respectively (Scott et al. 1985; Mildh et al. 2001). Blood concentrations of approximately 7 ng/mL or higher have been associated with fatal outcomes, particularly when polysubstance use is involved (Taylor 2005; European Union Drugs Agency 2025).

Biological effects and indications of fentanyl

In clinical practice, fentanyl is primarily utilized for its analgesic and anesthetic properties, which are predominantly attributed to its agonistic action on μ -opioid receptors (Frisoni et al. 2018). Chronic fentanyl use may induce opioid-induced hyperalgesia, characterized by a lowered pain threshold. Fentanyl-induced hyperalgesia poses a significant challenge in the clinical management of perioperative and chronic pain. Recent studies suggest that this phenomenon is modulated by the activation of extracellular signal-regulated kinase in the laterocapsular division of the central nucleus of the amygdala (CeLC), as well as CaMKII α in the CeLC–periaqueductal gray–rostral ventromedial medulla–spinal cord descending facilitative pain pathway in rat models (Li et al. 2017). At the same time, fentanyl and its analogs are highly addictive substances with a substantial potential for tolerance and dependence, which partly explains the sharp increase in misuse over recent years (Comer and Cahill 2019). Similar to other opioids, fentanyl induces drowsiness, a sense of relaxation, and euphoria, with the latter being less pronounced than that produced by endogenous opioids or morphine (Suzuki and El-Haddad 2016). Commonly reported side effects include migraine, dizziness, vertigo, confusion, and hallucinations, which can increase the risk of fractures in geriatric patients (Pergolizzi et al. 2008; Han et al. 2019). Additionally, other psychiatric disorders such as depression, insomnia, and suicidal tendencies may arise with prolonged misuse (Han et al. 2019).

Repeated administration may lead to gastrointestinal side effects such as nausea, vomiting, constipation,

postoperative ileus, and urinary retention (de Boer et al. 2017). Immunosuppression is also observed, which can be particularly dangerous in older adults and those already immunocompromised (Liu et al. 2006; Haroutounian 2018). Compared to morphine, fentanyl less frequently induces pruritus, which some authors attribute to its lower histamine release (Stanley 2014). Notable effects on the cardiovascular system have also been identified. Fentanyl can dose-dependently activate the vagus nerve, leading to increased parasympathetic activity and a reduction in heart rate. It may also cause hypotension through vasodilation (by decreasing sympathetic nervous system output) and inhibition of baroreceptor reflexes (Song et al. 2006). A potentially fatal consequence of fentanyl use is μ -receptor-mediated respiratory depression (Chen et al. 1993). Postural syncope and sudden onset of chest wall rigidity, particularly with intravenous administration, may occur. Chest wall rigidity ('wooden chest syndrome') can occur with intravenous doses as low as 50 μ g, with severity influenced by dose and rate of administration (Somerville et al. 2017; Schumacher and Fukuda 2019). Fentanyl misuse can lead to unusual symptoms, including acute anterograde amnesia, seizure activity, frothing at the mouth, diffuse alveolar hemorrhage following insufflation of fentanyl powder, or pulmonary alveolar proteinosis following smoking fentanyl (Kuczyńska et al. 2018). Withdrawal symptoms are characterized by sweating, anxiety, diarrhea, bone pain, abdominal cramps, and chills or „goose flesh“ (Suzuki and El-Haddad 2016; Abdulahim and Bowden-Jones 2018).

Given the dose-dependent effects of fentanyl on the body, opioids are generally prescribed at the lowest possible dose to ensure adequate therapeutic effect while improving the patient's quality of life. In the context of pain management, opioids are often combined with anticonvulsants, antidepressants, NSAIDs, and other adjunctive therapies, as well as non-pharmacological strategies (Benyamin et al. 2008). Today, intravenous fentanyl is the most commonly used opioid for intraoperative analgesia across Europe, North, Central, and South America, the Middle East, and significant portions of Asia and Africa. Transdermal fentanyl patches are frequently employed for the management of chronic pain in all forms of cancer. In this regard, recent studies indicate that fentanyl exhibits anti-leukemic activity and inhibits the viability of gastric and non-small cell lung cancer cells through the suppression of various intracellular signaling pathways (Gong et al. 2020; Li et al. 2020; Dai et al. 2021). However, fentanyl also stimulates tumor angiogenesis and promotes the migration of certain, but not all, tested human lung cancer cells, likely via the activation of multiple pro-angiogenic signaling pathways. This underscores the need for further research on its safe application in this patient population (Liu et al. 2020). Nevertheless, the opioid is indicated for the management of persistent, severe pain in a range of non-cancerous conditions. Rapid-onset transmucosal formulations, introduced in the last 30 years, have been specifically developed for the treatment of „breakthrough“ pain syndromes (Stanley 2014). Fentanyl is a key component of balanced anesthesia protocols due to its analgesic and sedative properties during general anesthesia procedures. In local anesthesia

techniques, fentanyl can enhance the effectiveness of local anesthetics, providing extended pain relief in specific areas of the body (Karunarathna 2024).

Analyzing the opioid crisis in the US, Bird et al. (2023) summarize that there is reason to believe that the consumption of illicit fentanyl significantly exceeds its use for medical purposes. Even more concerning is the fact that the composition of illegally produced fentanyl in confiscated samples varies considerably, reflecting the variability in exposure among individuals who misuse the substance (Bird et al. 2023). Additionally, fentanyl is often consumed in combination with other legal or illegal intoxicating substances. Alcohol and other drugs (e.g., cocaine, heroin) can synergistically exacerbate the side effects of fentanyl, creating complex, multi-layered clinical scenarios that often present complex clinical management challenges (Ramos-Matos 2024).

Conclusion

In conclusion, fentanyl has evolved from a highly potent analgesic developed in the 1960s to a widely used opioid with diverse clinical applications. Its ability to rapidly cross the blood-brain barrier and exhibit a broad spectrum of effects on opioid receptors has made it highly valuable in anesthesia and pain management. However, its high potency also contributes to significant risks, including addiction, overdose, and adverse side effects such as respiratory depression and cardiovascular instability. As fentanyl remains a critical tool in medical practice, especially for chronic pain management and breakthrough pain syndromes, ongoing research into its pharmacological profile and safer delivery methods is essential. Furthermore, the rise of illicit fentanyl has exacerbated the opioid crisis, underscoring the need for stricter regulation and a comprehensive approach to mitigate its misuse while optimizing its therapeutic potential.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, S.S.G.; methodology, S.S.G.; software, S.S.G.; formal analysis, S.S.; investigation, S.S.G., M.R-I., N.K.; resources, S.S.G., S. D. G. K., S. D. and M. P.; data curation, S.S.G.; writing—original draft preparation, S.S.G. and M. P.; writing—review and editing, S.S.G. and S. Z.; visualization, S.S.G.; supervision, P. M.; project administration, S.S.G.; funding acquisition, P.M. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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